

PROTOTYPE OF BIO-BASED PACKAGING AND PROTOCOL FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION

D5.13

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Short Description

This documentation forms the basis for the realization, implementation and management of four project prototypes of bio-based packaging. It includes the prototype objectives, general considerations and recommendations together with the following two sections:

- the prototype section that provides a scientific-technological description of the R&I process carried out to realize the prototype (final innovative method / system / tool / product) as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the in-field validation (WP5). According to the impact pathway approach, it describes the conducted activities, the reached outputs and outcomes, and the obtained measures of relevant key performance indicators demonstrating the impact;
- the protocol section that adopts an operational perspective to describe how to implement and manage the prototype, thus ensuring its full functionality and usability. It includes deployment requirements, procedures, methods, techniques, and practical considerations. Moreover, the protocols generate guidelines (D4.11), practice abstracts (D6.5) and training materials (D5.1).

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1. Background

1.1 Prototype motivations and objectives

Conventional packaging materials, especially single-use plastic, contribute significantly to worldwide environmental pollution. These materials often end up in oceans, landfills and ecosystems, where they harm animals and humans and contribute to environmental degradation (Fayshal, 2024). In fact, plastic bags are difficult and costly to recycle and most end up in the environment. They break down into tiny toxic particles that contaminate the soil and waterways and enter the food chain when animals accidentally ingest them (Pathak et al., 2025).

To address this pressing issue, the main objective was to develop sustainable and environmentally friendly packaging material prototypes using local raw materials (i.e., agricultural products, waste and by-products) that can be used to preserve the overall quality of food from different food hubs in Africa during the shelf-life.

The food packaging prototypes are based on bio-based and biodegradable polymers that offer numerous benefits including: reduced environmental impact, biodegradability, reduced carbon footprint, regulatory compliance and safety. In addition, the packaging solutions developed promote the valorisation of local agricultural biomass waste and by-products as simple and readily available raw materials. This approach supports the circular economy by turning waste into valuable resources and fostering local economic growth.

The bio-based packaging prototypes are in line with local policies and initiatives to reduce plastic waste and promote sustainability. By providing an environmentally friendly alternative, the prototypes improve local waste management and recycling systems, contributing to their efficiency and effectiveness. Adoption of the prototypes by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) helps consumers and public authorities to make sustainable choices that benefit both the environment and society. In addition, the proposed prototype fulfils several important consumer needs, especially those of health and environmentally conscious people. Today's consumers are increasingly demanding packaging solutions that minimise the impact on the environment while ensuring safety in direct contact with food and minimising the generation of food waste.

Overview of the bio-based packaging prototypes of the partner involved:

- the **INAT (TN)** team has developed a bio-based film using cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) made from wheat straw fibres, starch, polybutylene adipate co-terephthalate (PBAT), glycerol and antioxidant extract from artichoke by-products. The **wheat straw fibres cellulose nanocrystals-based film** prototype was used for the packaging of soft-dried fruits and vegetables, such as eggplants and strawberries.
- The **NARO (UG)** and **MAK (UG)** teams developed a bio-based a coating and a film made from starch extracted from bitter cassava roots, chitosan and glycerol. NARO tested **cassava starch- and chitosan-based coating and film** prototypes for the packaging of fish products (soft-smoked fish fillets and deep-fried fish fingers), while MAK applied the coating to whole fresh eggplants.

- The **UoN (KE)** team developed a packaging film consisting of starch extracted from cassava roots, coconut oil and glycerol. The **cassava starch- and coconut oil-based film** prototype was used for the packaging of dry foods such as tree tomato fruit powder (tamarillo) and deep-fried quinoa snacks (mandazi).
- The **SUA (TZ)** team developed a film made of nanocellulose obtained from pineapple peel waste, gellan gum and glycerol. The **pineapple peels nanocellulose-based film** prototype, in combination with a paper-based film (secondary packaging), was used for the packaging of dry foods such as extruded and non-extruded composite flours.

Some specific results have been archived on the Zenodo database as draft papers (working papers) in an encrypted folder with an embargo period, namely:

- Ines Ben Rejeb, Safa Baraketi, Raouia Ghanem, Mohamed Gargouri, Maria Alessia Schouten, Santina Romani, Faten Khammasi, Extraction of nanocrystalline cellulose (CNC) from agricultural waste as reinforcement ingredient for a chitosan-based nanocomposite films, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918282> [Zenodo, DOI].
- Ines Ben Rejeb, Safa Baraketi, Raouia Ghanem, Mohamed Gargouri, Maria Alessia Schouten, Santina Romani, Faten Khammasi, Development of a bio-based packaging material improved with wheat straw fibers nanocrystalline cellulose and artichoke by-product extract for food applications, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918348> [Zenodo, DOI].
- Nsubuga D., Chimoita E.L., Mugisha J., Gitau Magu M., Kimani J., Ben Rejeb I., Tinyiro S.E., Maitha I., Okoth M.W., Suleiman R., Schouten M.A., Setti M., Romani S., A comparative Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costing of selected bio-based packaging materials in comparison with an LDPE film, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918187> [Zenodo, DOI].
- Schouten M.A., Ben Rejeb I., Khammasi F., Tinyiro S.E., Aruho C., Kabenge I., Muyonga J., Maitha I., Okoth M.W., Mwanri A., Suleiman R., Nchimbi Msolla S., Setti M., Romani S., Sustainable food packaging system: Status of regulatory initiatives and issues on plastic use in Tunisia, Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania African countries, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918398> [Zenodo, DOI].

This decision has been taken to allow consortium researchers to utilize the data for the development of scientific publications in the period following the conclusion of the H2020 FoodLAND project. In the meantime, the corresponding DOI references have been provided to ensure data traceability and transparency, allowing interested researchers to access the materials as soon as they become available.

2. Prototype

Food Hub	Packaging material prototype	Food Product
Jendouba (TN)	Wheat straw fibres cellulose nanocrystals-based film (INAT)	Fruits and vegetables (soft-dried eggplants and strawberries) (INAT)
Kajjansi / Masaka (UG)	Cassava starch- and chitosan-based coating and film (NARO)	Fish products (soft-smoked fish fillets and fried fish fingers) (NARO)
Nakaseke (UG)	Cassava starch- and chitosan-based coating	Fruits and vegetables (fresh whole eggplants) (MAK)
Kitui (KE)	Cassava starch- and coconut oil-based film (UoN)	Therapeutic food (tree tomato fruit powder and quinoa snacks) (UoN)
Mvomero, Morogoro (TZ)	Pineapple peels nanocellulose-based film (SUA)	Composite flours (extruded and non-extruded) (SUA)

2.1 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

2.1.1 Wheat straw fibres cellulose nanocrystals-based film (INAT - TN)

The INAT team evaluated four raw materials for cellulose microfibrils (CMFs) production: pea hulls, artichoke by-products, olive tree by-products and wheat straw fibres (WSF). Based on moisture (~10%), cellulose content (~22.5%), and overall composition, WSF sourced from local agricultural companies (Jendouba, TN, region) was selected. The CMFs were further converted into cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs), in order to enhance the quality of bio-based packaging materials for the food industry.

CMFs were extracted via chemical treatment with sodium hydroxide and bleaching agents, while CNCs were obtained through sulfuric acid hydrolysis. Nanocomposite films were formulated by mixing chitosan (dissolved in acetic acid) with CNCs (1-10%) and casting the mixtures onto Petri dishes for room-temperature drying. The films were characterized for their physical and chemical properties, including FTIR analysis, thickness, moisture content, water solubility, transparency, colour, biodegradability, and mechanical strength.

For the film validation at semi-industrial scale, the formulation was optimized replacing chitosan with PBAT (polybutylene adipate terephthalate) and TPS (thermoplastic starch). Additionally, CNCs and an antioxidant extract from artichoke by-products (obtained via methanol maceration) were incorporated to enhance packaging material properties. The film was obtained using twin-screw extrusion and blown extrusion technologies. The formulation and production details are provided in D4.12 and in the updated D4.11.

The film prototype was tested for thickness, moisture, water solubility, mechanical properties (tensile force, breaking strength, tear resistance), coefficient of friction, migration test, water vapour permeability, biodegradability and FTIR analysis. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analysis were also carried out for the bio-based film prototype development in comparison to low-density polyethylene (LDPE)-based plastic material. In addition, shelf-life studies of soft-dried eggplants and strawberries packaged with the bio-based film prototype were carried out.

2.1.2 Cassava starch- and chitosan-based film and coating (NARO & MAK - UG)

The NARO team has developed a film and a coating bio-based packaging materials, both based on cassava starch and chitosan. The starch was extracted from cassava tubers (bitter varieties *Magana*) purchased from Kawempe market in Kampala (UG) through a wet process (**Figure 1**) following the operational procedures described in the updated D4.11, while the chitosan (from shrimp shells) was purchased.

Four different formulations were evaluated for film preparation: cassava starch/glycerol, cassava starch/glycerol/chitosan, cassava starch/glycerol/banana peels cellulose nanofiber and cassava starch/glycerol/chitosan/ banana peels cellulose nanofiber. Moreover, two coating formulations based on cassava starch/chitosan/glycerol with and without banana peels cellulose nanofiber were also prepared.

Extraction of starch from cassava tubers

Figure 1: Main steps of the starch extraction process from cassava tubers.

The differently formulated films and coatings were prepared according to the procedures reported in the Periodic Technical Report Part B and in the D4.12 (**Figure 2 and 3**).

Figure 2: Preparation of bio-based films: (a) casting the bio-based coating solution on plastic trays; (b) drying the casted solution in an oven; (c) example of film obtained.

The films were evaluated for: thickness, moisture content, transparency, colour, water activity, biodegradability, water solubility, water vapour transmission rate (WVTR), overall migration limit (OML) and mechanical properties (tensile stress, elongation at break and Young's modulus). The coating solutions were characterized for the viscosity in order to check the recommended (Budiman, 2011) optimal viscosity threshold of 113-225 centipoise. On the basis of the obtained characterization results, the best selected film and coating were: cassava starch/chitosan/glycerol (Periodic Technical Report Part B and D4.12). Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analysis were also carried out for the bio-based material prototypes development in comparison to low-density polyethylene (LDPE)-based plastic material. In addition, shelf-life studies of soft-smoked fish and deep-fried fish fingers coated and packaged with the bio-based material prototypes were carried out by NARO team. The MAK team also conducted a study on the shelf life of whole fresh eggplants coated with the optimised coating prototype.

Figure 3: Preparation of starch/chitosan/glycerol coating.

The validation activities took place with three fish processing SMEs and thirty fish farmers (some of whom also process and trade fish products) and aimed to demonstrate the production and application of the developed bio-based coating. This was done at both the NARO Kawanda (UG) laboratory and the Masaka (UG) Food Hub. The bio-based coating was chosen over the film as it performed better in the shelf-life studies. In addition, the coating is easier to prepare and handle than the bio-based film. During the demonstration, the coating was applied to the fish product by both dipping and brushing. Dipping is the most common method of applying the coating solution to the product as it is simple and does not require sophisticated equipment. However, this can result in wastage of the coating material, which is why the brushing alternative method application was also demonstrated.

2.1.3 Cassava starch- and coconut oil-based film (UoN - KE)

The UoN team has developed a new bio-based packaging prototype made from cassava starch, glycerol and coconut oil. Initially, the film material was formulated with only cassava starch and glycerol, but the addition of coconut oil improved the strength and reduced the hygroscopic nature of the previously formulated bio-based films (Periodic Technical Report Part B). The cassava tubers purchased from the Marigiti fresh produce market in Nairobi (KE) were characterized (for moisture, starch, crude protein, crude fat, crude fiber, ash) and wet-processed for starch extraction following the procedures described in the updated D4.11, while the coconut oil was purchased from the local market.

The bio-based film was prepared according to the procedures reported in the updated D4.11. The main steps of bio-based film production are shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4: Main steps of cassava starch/coconut oil-based film production.

The film prototype was optimized for its thickness (150 vs 200 μm) and tested for moisture content, transparency, water solubility, biodegradability, water vapor transmission rate, mechanical and sealing properties.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analysis were also carried out for the selected bio-based film prototype (selected thickness of 200 μm) development in comparison to low-density polyethylene (LDPE)-based plastic material. In addition, shelf-life studies of which tree tomato fruit powder (tamarillo) and deep-fried quinoa snacks (mandazi) packaged with the bio-based film prototype were carried out.

The validation activities took place at the Kitui (KE) Food Hub, part of the Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Ltd (KEPC) factory, with the participation of 38 farmers. The cassava starch/coconut oil-based film material was produced in the UoN lab and used to package tree tomato fruit powder as part of a demonstration at the KEPC facility. The UoN team, assisted by KEPC production staff, demonstrated to the participants how the film pouches are made from cassava, coconut oil and glycerol. The farmers were also asked to answer an acceptance questionnaire on some characteristics of the bio-based packaging prototype.

2.1.4 Pineapple peels nanocellulose-based film (SUA - TZ)

The SUA team has developed a new bio-based packaging material with nanocellulose extracted from pineapple peels (PPs), a local by-product. After physico-chemical

characterisation of the PPs (moisture, ash, lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose, density, water absorption, water solubility index), the cellulose was isolated by cleaning, drying and grinding the peels into a powder, followed by a multi-step chemical treatment to extract and purify the cellulose. For the production of PPs nanocellulose (PPnc), acid hydrolysis was performed as described in the updated D4.11.

The bio-based film was formulated with gellan gum, glycerol and different PPnc concentrations according to the procedures described in the Periodic Technical Report Part B. The developed films were tested for thickness, moisture, transparency, opacity, colour, water solubility, acid solubility, alkaline solubility, biodegradability, water vapour transmission rate, tensile strength, Young's Modulus and elongation at break. The best bio-based film prototype was selected (12% PPnc of gellan gum, w/w) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analysis were also carried out for the bio-based film prototype development in comparison to low-density polyethylene (LDPE)-based plastic material. In addition, shelf-life studies of two composite flours for the preparation of porridge (i. extruded and ii. non-extruded) packaged with the bio-based film prototype were carried out.

The validation activities took place at Katundu Traders Ltd (Morogoro, TZ), which specialises in the milling/packaging of various types of flour and showed interest in the developed packaging material prototype. During the demonstration of the PPnc-based film, a single sample with 8% PPnc (gellan gum, w/w) was shown. The 8% concentration of gellan gum was used to reduce production costs and provide a clearer film compared to the 12% concentration of PPnc (gellan gum, w/w) used in the shelf-life study. The PPnc-based film was produced in the SUA laboratory and partly at Katundu Traders Ltd.

2.2 Summary of the outputs

2.2.1 Results and achievements

2.2.1.1 INAT (TN)

Properties of packaging materials

The properties of the two bio-based films produced (PBAT + TPS and PBAT + TPS + CNCs + artichoke by-product extract) were evaluated. The results show that the PBAT + TPS film has a higher moisture content than the film enriched with CNCs and artichoke extract. The addition of CNCs reduced water solubility and had an overall migration limit that complied with European food contact regulations. While both bio-based films were inhomogeneous in thickness, tensile tests showed that the film with CNCs and artichoke by-product extract was more flexible and resistant. The tensile strength and water vapour permeability were higher for the activated film. However, both bio-based films required a slippery agent in the formulation to improve the surface condition and facilitate the packaging operation for future use. Biodegradability tests showed that both films tended to biodegrade (34.86% after 18 weeks). Specific results on the properties of the realised bio-based films are reported in the D4.12 and in the updated D4.11.

Shelf-life tests

Shelf-life studies were carried out on soft-dried eggplants and strawberries packed with pouches made from the control film (PBAT + TPS) and the sample film (PBAT + TPS + CNCs + artichoke extract) (Figure 5) compared to the same food products packed in commercially available polypropylene pouches. The differently packaged food products were stored for 4 months at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) and at 35 °C and analysed after 0, 10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 and 120 days for some quality parameters (weight loss, total phenolic compounds and DPPH antioxidant activity).

A total of 14 pouches were prepared for each product and all quality parameters were analysed in triplicate.

Soft-dried eggplants

After 4 months of storage, all samples of the packaged soft-dried eggplants showed a weight loss of about 7 % at room temperature and 14 % at 35 °C.

At the end of the 4th month storage period, the total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant (DPPH) underwent a fictitious increase due to the sample concentration caused by the weight/water loss. When stored at room temperature, the TPC and DPPH values of the eggplants packed in the sample pouch were similar to those packed in PP pouch. Specific results can be found in the Zenodo database at the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918348>.

Figure 5: (a) Sealing machine for the production of pouches; (b) soft-dried eggplants packed in the bio-based packaging prototype; (c) soft-dried strawberries before packaging; (d) soft-dried strawberries packed in the bio-based packaging prototype.

Soft-dried strawberries

After 120 days at room temperature, the weight loss of strawberries packaged with the active sample film (PBAT + TPS + CNCs + artichoke extract) was about 7 %, lower than the control (PBAT + TPS) at 9 % and the commercial packaging (polypropylene) at 9 %. At higher storage temperatures (35 °C), this trend continued, demonstrating the good performance of the active film prototype in reducing the weight loss of the product (15 % vs 16 and 17 % average weight loss, respectively).

Similar to the eggplants, the total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant (DPPH) of the soft-dried strawberries increased at the end of the 4th month of storage due to the sample concentration caused by the weight/water loss. When stored at 21 °C, the TPC values of strawberries packed in active sample pouches were lower than those of strawberries packed in control and commercial pouches. After four months of storage at 35 °C, no differences were found between the samples. In terms of antioxidant activity, the sample packed with the bio-based activated material showed a higher value than the other samples both at 21 and 35 °C after 4 months of storage. Specific results can be found in the Zenodo database at the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918348>.

In future studies, a more in-depth shelf-life study should be conducted to further investigate the effects of the new packaging materials on microbial growth and other quality characteristics of the food products during shelf-life (e.g. moisture, water activity, colour, texture, etc.).

2.2.1.2 NARO and MAK (UG)

Proprieties of packaging materials

The properties of the developed bio-based films and coatings were characterised. The results showed that the four bio- packaging film samples varied in thickness (0.17-0.27

mm), with cassava starch/glycerol/chitosan/nanocellulose being significantly thicker than the others. The transparency ranged from 15.6 % to 42.7 %, the moisture content (15.5-17.7 %) and the water activity (0.63-0.72). However, the high values for water solubility indicate poor structural integrity in aqueous environments. In addition, the film samples exhibited moderate mechanical properties, so an improvement in tensile strength and water resistance is required for extended future applications. Nevertheless, the films were highly biodegradable (91.7-97.7% after 12 days). Based on the overall results (D4.12 and updated D4.11), the cassava starch/chitosan/glycerol formulation was selected for both the film and the coating and used for the fish product shelf-life study. The specific results are reported in the Periodic Technical Report Part B, D4.12 and in the updated D4.11.

Shelf-life tests (fish products)

The effects of the bio-based packaging materials, including the optimised film and coating, on the shelf life of soft-smoked fish fillets and deep-fried fish fingers were evaluated (**Figure 6**). Both fish products were packed with four different packaging materials: i) control - uncoated and wrapped in LDPE film, ii) coated and wrapped in LDPE film, iii) uncoated and wrapped in bio-based film and iv) coated and wrapped in bio-based film (**Table 1**).

The coating was applied by dipping individual pieces of fish into the coating solution at room temperature for approximately 4 seconds, followed by a 10-minute drying period. Approximately 1 L of the bio-based coating was required to coat 1 kg of fish product.

For packaging, 100 g fish samples were placed on white polystyrene trays and wrapped in either LDPE or bio-based film. Each packaging condition was prepared in triplicate for six sampling times, so that a total of 48 samples were available for both soft-smoked fish fillets and deep-fried fish fingers.

The samples were stored in a refrigerator for 15 days, with temperature and relative humidity fluctuating throughout the storage period (**Figure 7**). The temperature ranged from 3.6 to 8 °C (average 5.6 ± 1.2 °C), while the relative humidity varied between 38% and 65% (average $53.6 \pm 7.8\%$).

The fish products were analysed under different packaging conditions every three days (0, 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 days) to determine the main physico-chemical and microbiological quality parameters. These included moisture content, water activity, pH, peroxide value, total viable count, yeast and molds count and sensory characteristics (appearance, taste, aroma, texture and overall acceptability). All analyses were carried out in triplicate.

Figure 6: (a) Soft-smoked fish fillets coated with the bio-based coating and packed in the bio-based film prototype; (b) deep-fried fish fingers coated with the bio-based coating and packed in the bio-based film prototype.

Table 1: Packaging conditions and fish products for shelf-life study with corresponding sample code.

Packaging conditions	Food products	
Control: un-coated samples in polystyrene (PS) tray and LDPE wrapping	Soft-smoked fillet (UCSSF)	Deep-fried fish fingers (UCDFF)
<u>Coated</u> samples in PS tray and LDPE wrapping	Soft-smoked fillet (CSSF)	Deep-fried fish fingers (CDFF)
Un-coated samples in PS tray and <u>bio-based film wrapping</u>	Soft-smoked fillet (UCSSF+BBF)	Deep-fried fish fingers (UCDFF+BBF)
<u>Coated</u> samples in PS tray and <u>bio-based film wrapping</u>	Soft-smoked fillet (CSSF+BBF)	Deep-fried fish fingers (CDFF+BBF)

Figure 7: Relative humidity (%) and temperature (°C) conditions during cold storage of fish products.

The main quality characteristics of the two fish products at initial time (0 day) are reported in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Initial main quality characteristics of soft-smoked fish fillets and deep-fried fish fingers uncoated and coated with the bio-based coating prototype.

	Soft smoked fish fillets		Deep fried fish fingers	
	Uncoated	Coated	Uncoated	Coated
Moisture (%)	66.4 ± 1.2 ^a	60.7 ± 2.1 ^b	57.9 ± 1.4 ^A	58.4 ± 1.6 ^A
Water activity (a _w)	0.86 ± 0.02 ^a	0.91 ± 0.01 ^b	0.93 ± 0.00 ^A	0.91 ± 0.01 ^B
pH	6.7 ± 0.03 ^a	6.5 ± 0.01 ^b	6.6 ± 0.2 ^A	6.1 ± 0.1 ^B
Peroxide value (meq O ₂ /kg oil)	7.5 ± 3.7 ^a	5.3 ± 3.6 ^a	16.2 ± 9.2 ^A	15.9 ± 6.5 ^A
TPC (log UFC/g)	1.4 ± 0.01 ^a	1.3 ± 0.03 ^a	3.8 ± 0.04 ^A	3.3 ± 0.15 ^A
Yeasts and molds (log UFC/g)	1.2 ± 0.1 ^a	0.8 ± 0.05 ^a	1.7 ± 0.1 ^A	1.9 ± 0.7 ^A

Different letter indicates significant difference among the sample.

Soft-smoked fish fillets

The soft-smoked fish fillets with acceptable levels of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH) were prepared using a slightly modified method of Masette et al. (2018) using the NARO PAH-Safe Fish Smoking Kiln. The fish fillets were immersed in a previously prepared brine solution (500 g of salt in 20 L of water) for 30 min. The fish was placed on stainless steel racks to allow drainage of excess water, removed and arranged into the smoking kiln. The smoke was generated using banana peels and fresh guava wood. The fish was exposed to the smoke at 40 °C for 1 h and the temperature in the kiln was gradually increased to 70 °C for 4 h to allow partial dehydration of the fish (D4.12).

The results of soft-smoked fish fillets shelf-life test are reported in **Figures 8, 9 and 10**.

a)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCSSF	^B 66.4±1.2 ^a	^{AB} 68.0±1.5 ^a	^B 66.2±0.9 ^a	^A 71.8±1.5 ^a	^{AB} 67.7±2.0 ^{ab}	^B 67.2±1.6 ^b
CSSF	^A 60.7±2.1 ^b	^{BC} 54.8±0.3 ^c	^C 54.1±1.5 ^b	^{AB} 59.0±1.5 ^b	^{AB} 59.2±0.4 ^c	^{ABC} 58.0±3.1 ^c
UCSSF+BBF	^B 66.4±1.2 ^a	^B 68.7±1.2 ^a	^B 66.6±1.8 ^a	^B 69.5±1.4 ^a	^B 70.2±1.5 ^a	^A 76.8±2.2 ^a
CSSF+BBF	^{DE} 60.7±2.1 ^b	^E 57.7±0.8 ^b	^{CD} 63.6±0.2 ^a	^{AB} 68.3±1.5 ^a	^{BC} 65.4±0.2 ^b	^A 71.1±0.8 ^{ab}

b)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCSSF	^C 0.86±0.02 ^b	^{BC} 0.88±0.03 ^b	^A 0.94±0.01 ^c	^A 0.94±0.01 ^b	^{AB} 0.92±0.01 ^a	^{AB} 0.93±0.02 ^a
CSSF	^C 0.91±0.01 ^a	^B 0.94±0.00 ^a	^A 0.98±0.00 ^a	^{AB} 0.97±0.00 ^a	^B 0.94±0.01 ^a	^{BC} 0.94±0.03 ^a
UCSSF+BBF	^C 0.86±0.02 ^b	^C 0.87±0.01 ^b	^A 0.95±0.00 ^b	^B 0.91±0.01 ^c	^B 0.92±0.01 ^a	^C 0.87±0.00 ^b
CSSF+BBF	^B 0.91±0.01 ^a	^{AB} 0.93±0.01 ^a	^A 0.95±0.00 ^b	^{BC} 0.91±0.00 ^c	^B 0.92±0.01 ^a	^C 0.88±0.02 ^b

c)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCSSF	^B 6.7±0.03 ^a	^A 6.9±0.01 ^a	^B 6.7±0.01 ^a	^B 6.7±0.03 ^a	^B 6.7±0.00 ^b	^B 6.7±0.00 ^a
CSSF	^D 6.5±0.01 ^b	^A 6.7±0.00 ^c	^B 6.6±0.00 ^b	^C 6.6±0.01 ^b	^C 6.6±0.00 ^c	^E 6.3±0.00 ^d
UCSSF+BBF	^C 6.7±0.03 ^a	^B 6.7±0.01 ^b	^B 6.7±0.00 ^a	^D 6.6±0.00 ^{ab}	^A 6.8±0.00 ^a	^D 6.6±0.01 ^b
CSSF+BBF	^C 6.5±0.01 ^b	^A 6.7±0.00 ^c	^B 6.6±0.00 ^c	^D 6.4±0.01 ^c	^D 6.4±0.01 ^d	^E 6.3±0.01 ^c

d)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCSSF	^{AB} 7.5±3.7 ^a	^{AB} 5.3±3.6 ^a	^A 13.0±3.7 ^a	^{AB} 8.7±3.7 ^a	^{AB} 9.9±0.1 ^a	^B 3.3±0.0 ^a
CSSF	^A 5.3±3.6 ^a	^A 9.8±6.5 ^a	^A 4.4±0.1 ^a	^A 6.6±0.0 ^a	^A 7.6±3.8 ^a	^A 5.4±3.7 ^a
UCSSF+BBF	^A 7.5±3.7 ^a	^A 5.3±3.6 ^a	^A 6.6±3.8 ^a	^A 6.6±0.2 ^a	^A 14.2±3.9 ^a	^A 9.9±6.6 ^a
CSSF+BBF	^A 5.3±3.6 ^a	^A 5.5±3.8 ^a	^A 8.6±7.4 ^a	^A 11.0±3.8 ^a	^A 14.0±3.5 ^a	^A 9.8±6.5 ^a

Figure 8: (a) Moisture content; (b) water activity; (c) pH values; (d) peroxide value of soft-smoked fish fillets packaged under different conditions during shelf-life testing. In tables, capital letters indicate significant differences within the same row, while lower case letters indicate significant differences within the same column ($p \leq 0.05$).

The moisture content of soft-smoked fish fillet samples during the shelf-life was in the range 54.1 to 76.8% (**Figure 8a**). The moisture content of the coated sample, which was wrapped in conventional LDPE film (CSSF), remained significantly lower. The highest increase in moisture content during the storage period of 15 days was obtained in the samples wrapped with bio-based film (UCSSF+BBF and CSSF+BBF). This could be attributed to the low water barrier of the bio-based materials.

The water activity (a_w) of the soft smoked fillets was in the range 0.86 to 0.98 across all sample packaging and storage time (**Figure 8b**). The a_w of coated soft-smoked fish in LDPE packaging (CSSF) increased significantly during the first 6 days of storage compared to uncoated fish in the same conventional packaging (UCSSF). This could be related to the migration of moisture from the coating into the product (Tinyiro et al., 2016). At the end of the shelf life (15 days), the CSSF and UCSSF samples show similar a_w values. Similarly, the UCSSF+BBF and CSSF+BBF samples show no significant differences at the end of storage, confirming their similarity.

The pH value of the soft smoked fish samples varied from 6.27 to 6.87 (**Figure 8c**). Regardless of the packaging conditions, the pH remained within the expected neutral range, as reported by Rodrigues De Souza et al. (2020) for smoked fish products.

The results of the peroxide value (PV) showed only slight significantly differences between all the samples (**Figure 8d**), which remained within the recommended limit of 20 meq O_2/kg oil (Connell, 1975).

a)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCSSF	^{CD} 1.4±0.01 ^a	^D 1.0±0.00 ^c	^B 2.2±0.25 ^a	^B 1.9±0.06 ^b	^{BC} 1.8±0.21 ^b	^A 4.1±0.01 ^a
CSSF	^C 1.3±0.03 ^a	^B 2.3±0.03 ^b	^B 2.5±0.12 ^a	^A 3.3±0.05 ^a	^D 1.0±0.00 ^c	^D 1.0±0.00 ^c
UCSSF+BBF	^D 1.4±0.01 ^a	^C 2.2±0.03 ^b	^C 2.0±0.03 ^a	^B 2.9±0.14 ^a	^A 3.6±0.01 ^a	^A 3.6±0.21 ^b
CSSF+BBF	^{DE} 1.3±0.03 ^a	^A 3.1±0.18	^B 2.3±0.04 ^a	^C 1.8±0.01 ^b	^{CD} 1.7±0.03 ^b	^E 1.0±0.00 ^c

b)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCSSF	^C 1.2±0.11 ^a	^A 2.4±0.14 ^{ab}	^C 1.0±0.00 ^a	^C 1.0±0.05 ^a	^C 1.0±0.03 ^c	^B 1.7±0.03 ^a
CSSF	^A 1.3±0.05 ^a	^A 1.0±0.00 ^b	^A 1.1±0.00 ^a	^A 1.0±0.01 ^a	^A 1.0±0.02 ^c	^A 1.0±0.22 ^b
UCSSF+BBF	^B 1.2±0.11 ^a	^A 2.0±0.46 ^{ab}	^B 1.0±0.00 ^a	^B 1.0±0.00 ^a	^A 2.0±0.21 ^a	^B 1.0±0.02 ^b
CSSF+BBF	^B 1.3±0.05 ^a	^A 2.9±0.72 ^a	^B 1.0±0.00 ^a	^B 1.0±0.02 ^a	^{AB} 1.7±0.03 ^b	^B 1.0±0.13 ^b

Figure 9: (a) Total plate count and (b) yeasts and molds count of soft smoked fish fillets packaged under different conditions during shelf-life testing. In tables, capital letters indicate significant differences within the same row, while lower case letters indicate significant differences within the same column ($p \leq 0.05$).

The microbiological quality results (**Figure 9**) showed that the total plate count (TPC) of soft-smoked fish fillet remained within the acceptable US EAS (2017) limit of <5 Log CFU/g throughout the storage period, regardless of the packaging conditions (**Figure 9a**). The highest TPC of 4.10 and 3.59 Log CFU/g were reached on day 15 for the uncoated samples (UCSSF and UCSSF+BBF). The coated samples under conventional and bio-based film packaging showed a significantly lower TPC ($p \leq 0.05$) than the uncoated samples. Chitosan is one of the main components of the coating and, according to Ke et al. (2021), has antimicrobial properties. Yeast and molds count was within the acceptable limit of 3 log CFU/g for all packaging conditions (**Figure 9b**). The

yeast and mould count of the sample wrapped with LDPE film (CSSF) was stable throughout the storage period and showed no significant differences until day 15, while the other samples showed some differences during the storage period.

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCSSF	^A 7.7±1.1 ^a	^A 7.6±0.7 ^a	^A 7.3±0.5 ^a	^A 6.7±1.1 ^a	^A 6.8±0.8 ^a	^A 7.2±0.7 ^a
CSSF	^A 7.4±1.3 ^a	^A 7.4±1.3 ^a	^A 6.9±0.7 ^a	^A 7.1±1.3 ^a	^A 6.6±1.2 ^a	^A 7.3±0.9 ^a
UCSSF+BBF	^A 7.7±1.1 ^a	^A 6.9±1.3 ^a	^A 6.9±0.9 ^a	^A 6.5±1.3 ^a	^A 6.8±1.8 ^a	^A 6.5±1.1 ^a
CSSF+BBF	^A 7.4±1.3 ^a	^A 7.9±1.1 ^a	^A 7.3±0.7 ^a	^A 6.7±1.2 ^a	^A 7.2±0.9 ^a	^A 7.3±0.7 ^a

Figure 10: Sensory acceptability of soft smoked fish fillets packaged under different conditions during shelf-life testing. In tables, capital letters indicate significant differences within the same row, while lower case letters indicate significant differences within the same column ($p \leq 0.05$).

The sensory acceptability of soft-smoked fish fillets packaged under different conditions remained above the minimum acceptable threshold of 5 throughout the storage period (**Figure 10**). The results indicate that no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed among the samples differently packaged, suggesting that all conditions effectively preserved the sensory attributes of the product over 15 days of refrigerated storage.

Deep-fried fish fingers

The fish fingers were prepared according to the method by Amal et al. (2020) with slight modifications. The fish fillets were manually boned, cut into finger shapes and dipped into the pre-prepared batter solution. The batter solution was prepared by mixing 8% wheat flour, 10% egg white and 2% spices (black pepper, white pepper, fish masala, garlic powder and salt in equal proportions). The battered fish was then rolled in 10%

breadcrumbs. 250 g portions of the battered and breaded fish fingers were then deep fried in soya bean oil (1 litre) at 200 °C for 5 min. The oil was changed after every 3 frying cycles (D4.12).

The results of fried fish samples shelf-life test are reported in **Figures 11, 12 and 13.**

a)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCDF	AB57.9±1.4 ^a	A58.4±2.0 ^a	D51.7±0.6 ^b	BCD54.6±1.0 ^b	ABC55.4±1.0 ^b	CD52.6±1.1 ^b
CDF	A58.4±1.6 ^a	A58.2±0.3 ^a	A60.2±1.0 ^a	A58.2±2.8 ^{ab}	A58.5±1.3 ^{ab}	B52.6±2.5 ^b
UCDF+BBF	C57.9±1.4 ^a	D52.1±1.3 ^b	E48.4±0.7 ^c	BC59.9±1.6 ^a	AB62.3±1.0 ^a	A65.0±1.7 ^a
CDF+BBF	B58.4±1.6 ^a	C52.0±1.2 ^b	B60.0±0.6 ^a	B59.8±1.2 ^a	AB60.6±2.4 ^a	A64.6±1.8 ^a

b)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCDFF	^D 0.93±0.00 ^a	^C 0.95±0.01 ^b	^B 0.97±0.00 ^a	^B 0.97±0.00 ^a	^A 0.99±0.00 ^a	^{AB} 0.98±0.01 ^a
CDFF	^D 0.91±0.01 ^b	^C 0.95±0.01 ^b	^B 0.96±0.00 ^a	^{AB} 0.97±0.01 ^a	^A 0.99±0.00 ^a	^B 0.97±0.01 ^{ab}
UCDFF+BBF	^C 0.93±0.00 ^a	^A 0.97±0.00 ^a	^A 0.97±0.00 ^a	^{AB} 0.96±0.00 ^a	^{BC} 0.95±0.00 ^c	^C 0.94±0.01 ^{bc}
CDFF+BBF	^C 0.91±0.01 ^b	^B 0.95±0.00 ^b	^A 0.97±0.01 ^a	^{AB} 0.97±0.00 ^a	^{AB} 0.97±0.01 ^b	^C 0.91±0.02 ^c

c)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCDFF	^A 6.6±0.20 ^a	^{BC} 6.5±0.01 ^a	^B 6.5±0.00 ^a	^C 6.5±0.01 ^a	^B 6.5±0.01 ^a	^D 6.4±0.01 ^a
CDFF	^{CD} 6.1±0.10 ^b	^{AB} 6.2±0.00 ^d	^D 6.1±0.00 ^d	^A 6.2±0.01 ^a	^{AB} 6.2±0.00 ^d	^{BC} 6.1±0.01 ^d
UCDFF+BBF	^{AB} 6.6±0.20 ^a	^{AB} 6.4±0.01 ^b	^{AB} 6.5±0.00 ^b	^A 6.7±0.22 ^a	^{AB} 6.3±0.00 ^b	^B 6.2±0.00 ^c
CDFF+BBF	^D 6.1±0.10 ^b	^C 6.2±0.01 ^c	^A 6.4±0.00 ^c	^D 6.1±0.01 ^a	^B 6.3±0.00 ^c	^B 6.3±0.00 ^b

d)

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCDFF	^A 15.9±6.5 ^a	^A 14.2±3.8 ^{bc}	^A 10.9±0.1 ^b	^A 13.2±0.1 ^b	^A 7.7±3.8 ^b	^A 16.2±6.4 ^b
CDFF	^{BC} 16.2±9.2 ^a	^B 25.1±3.9 ^b	^{BC} 19.6±3.5 ^b	^C 9.8±3.7 ^b	^C 12.0±3.5 ^b	^A 44.7±4.1 ^a
UCDFF+BBF	^B 15.9±6.5 ^a	^B 11.8±3.5 ^c	^B 8.9±3.8 ^b	^B 8.8±3.8 ^b	^B 5.5±3.7 ^b	^A 51.1±9.8 ^a
CDFF+BBF	^C 16.2±9.2 ^a	^B 42.3±7.1 ^a	^A 69.1±12.4 ^a	^A 65.6±3.7 ^a	^A 71.1±4.8 ^a	^B 46.6±7.3 ^a

Figure 11: (a) Moisture content; (b) water activity; (c) pH values; (d) peroxide value of deep-fried fish fingers packaged under different conditions during shelf-life testing. In tables, capital letters indicate significant differences within the same row, while lower case letters indicate significant differences within the same column ($p \leq 0.05$).

The moisture content of the deep-fried fish samples varied between 48.4 and 65.0% during the storage period (**Figure 11a**). At the end of storage, the samples wrapped in bio-based film (UCDFF+BBF and CDFF+BBF) were found to have the highest moisture content values. Similar to the soft-smoked fish fingers, this could be due to the low water barrier of the bio-based film, which allowed moisture migration between the packaging film and the external environment.

The a_w value of the deep-fried fish fingers varied between 0.91 and 0.99 depending on the packaging conditions and storage time (**Figure 11b**).

The pH value of the deep-fried fish finger samples during storage was in the range of 6.08-6.65 (**Figure 11c**). The coated samples (CDFF and CDFF + BBF) had a slight lower pH, which is due to the acidic pH of the coating solution. The pH of the coated deep-fried fish sample wrapped in conventional LDPE film was the most stable during storage, showing no significant net change between days 0 and 15.

The PV value of uncoated fried fish wrapped in conventional LDPE film (UCDFF) was most stable throughout storage and remained within the recommended limit of 20 meq O_2 /kg oil (Connell, 1975) (**Figure 11d**). Similarly, the sample of uncoated fried fish wrapped with bio-based film (UCDFF+BBF) was stable during the first 12 days. The PV of the coated deep-fried fish fingers wrapped in bio-based film (CDFF+BBF) increased exponentially during the first 6 days of storage, reaching a peak value of 70 meq O_2 /kg oil, data that must be confirmed with further trials.

a)

	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCDF	^{BC} 3.8±0.05 ^a	^D 3.0±0.07 ^b	^E 2.3±0.23 ^c	^{CD} 3.4±0.04 ^{ab}	^A 5.0±0.00 ^b	^B 4.0±0.00 ^b
CDF	^C 3.3±0.15 ^a	^C 3.4±0.15 ^a	^D 2.5±0.02 ^{bc}	^E 1.8±0.02 ^b	^A 4.5±0.03 ^c	^B 3.9±0.08 ^b
UCDF+BBF	^C 3.8±0.05 ^a	^E 1.0±0.00 ^c	^D 2.8±0.01 ^{ab}	^C 4.0±0.00 ^a	^B 5.6±0.01 ^a	^A 6.8±0.00 ^a
CDF+BBF	^A 3.3±0.15 ^a	^A 3.2±0.02 ^{ab}	^A 3.2±0.03 ^a	^A 2.6±0.87 ^{ab}	^B 1.0±0.00 ^d	^{AB} 1.9±0.01 ^c

b)

	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCDF	^B 1.7±0.10 ^a	^B 2.2±0.03 ^a	^C 1.0±0.01 ^c	^A 3.6±0.01 ^b	^A 4.0±0.06 ^c	^B 2.0±0.03 ^b
CDF	^B 1.9±0.7 ^a	^C 1.0±0.20 ^b	^B 1.7±0.03 ^b	^C 1.0±0.05 ^d	^A 4.7±0.10 ^b	^C 1.0±0.20 ^c
UCDF+BBF	^E 1.7±0.00 ^a	^D 1.0±0.00 ^b	^C 3.4±0.01 ^a	^B 5.6±0.20 ^a	^B 5.6±0.02 ^a	^A 7.0±0.05 ^a
CDF+BBF	^A 1.9±0.04 ^a	^A 2.1±0.52 ^a	^B 1.0±0.00 ^c	^{AB} 1.7±0.03 ^c	^A 2.0±0.03 ^d	^B 1.0±0.01 ^c

Figure 12: (a) Total plate count and (b) yeasts and molds count of deep-fried fish fingers packaged under different conditions during shelf-life testing. In tables, capital letters indicate significant differences within the same row, while lower case letters indicate significant differences within the same column ($p \leq 0.05$).

The microbiological quality results showed that the total plate count (TPC) of the coated deep-fried fish finger samples (CDFF and CDFF+BBF) and the uncoated sample wrapped in LDPE film remained within acceptable limits throughout the storage period (**Figure 12a**). The TPC of the uncoated samples wrapped in bio-based film increased and exceeded the acceptable limit on day 12.

The yeast and molds count (**Figure 12b**) of coated deep-fried fish wrapped with biodegradable packaging (CDFF+BBF) was the most stable throughout storage and was the only one that stayed within the specification limit of 3 Log CFU/g during the entire storage period. The coated deep-fried fish fingers wrapped with conventional LDPE film (CDFF) was within acceptable limits for at least 9 days. Moreover, the uncoated sample wrapped with bio-based film (UCDFF+BBF) had the highest counts from the 6th day of storage.

In terms of sensory quality (**Figure 13**), it was found that on the average the UDFB+BBF sample was the less appreciated by panellists. This is probably due to the deterioration of the chemical and microbial composition of the fish. In fact, the deep-fried sample, which was not coated but wrapped with the bio-based film (UCDFF+BBF), was no longer included in the sensory evaluation after the 12th day, as it already had clearly visible molds.

Day:	0	3	6	9	12	15
UCDFF	^A 8.8±0.6 ^a	^{AB} 7.9±0.9 ^a	^B 7.7±0.5 ^{ab}	^B 7.4±0.9 ^a	^B 7.7±0.8 ^{ab}	^B 7.3±0.7 ^a

CDF	^A 7.7±0.9 ^b	^A 8.3±0.8 ^a	^A 7.2±1.0 ^b	^A 8.0±0.7 ^a	^A 7.5±0.5 ^{ab}	^A 7.6±1.0 ^a
UCDF+BBF	^A 8.8±0.9 ^a	^B 7.5±0.7 ^a	^{AB} 8.3±0.9 ^a	^{AB} 7.9±0.8 ^a	^{AB} 7.9±0.8 ^a	NA
CDF+BBF	^{AB} 7.7±0.6 ^b	^A 8.3±1.0 ^a	^{AB} 7.7±0.8 ^{ab}	^{AB} 7.7±0.6 ^a	^B 6.8±0.9 ^b	^{AB} 7.5±1.0 ^a

Figure 13: Sensory acceptability of deep-fried fish fingers packaged under different conditions during shelf-life testing. In tables, capital letters indicate significant differences within the same row, while lower case letters indicate significant differences within the same column ($p \leq 0.05$).

Overall, based on this study, it is recommended that the bio-based coating can be further explored for application in SMEs/processors due to its positive impact on product shelf life. In general, the bio-based coating has the potential to extend the shelf life of both processed fish products, especially when combined with LDPE film.

The bio-based film was also promising, but needs further improvement, especially in terms of moisture resistance as well as mechanical properties, sealability and transparency/colour properties.

Shelf-life test (fresh whole eggplants)

Shelf-life studies were also carried out on fresh whole eggplants coated with the optimal coating solution developed and supplied by the NARO laboratories.

A total of 15 kg of freshly harvested whole eggplants were supplied by a farmer from Nakaseke (UG) food hub (**Figure 14a**). The eggplants received were sorted to eliminate the bruised, punctured and those with any visible physical damage. The eggplants that had no blemishes (approx. 10 kg) were cleaned by washing them in washing water containing 1% calcium hypochlorite and then dried prior to coating. Half (approximately 5 kg) of the eggplants were coated by dipping for 5 seconds. After the dipping process, the eggplants were placed on perforated polystyrene trays to allow excess coating to drain and left to stand for 30 minutes at room temperature to dry (**Figure 14b**). The other eggplants were not dipped as a control sample (**Figure 14c**). Both the dipped and undipped eggplants were placed in a perforated plastic basket. Half (approximately 2.5 kg) were stored under refrigeration (approximately 7 ± 2 °C) and half at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) for 20 days. Triplicate samples from each lot were taken at intervals of 4 days and analysed for weight loss, moisture content, texture (hardness), pH, vitamin C content, total soluble solids, total plate counts, yeast and molds count.

Figure 14: (a) Coated and (b) uncoated (control sample) eggplants at day 0.

The comparison of the chemical and physical properties of coated and uncoated eggplants stored at room and refrigerated temperatures showed that all measured parameters changed over time and that the coating had minimal effect on the eggplant properties, while refrigeration slowed down the overall quality decay (**Table 3**).

The moisture content of coated and uncoated eggplants stored under different storage conditions decreased over time, with the samples stored at room temperature showing a greater decrease. However, it was found that the coating generally had no effect on the rate of moisture loss in the eggplants stored at both room and refrigerated temperatures.

At room temperature, the coating had an effect on the rate of weight loss during the first 16 days of storage. In addition, the coating had no significant effect on the rate of weight loss during storage in the refrigerator. No differences were found between coated and uncoated samples and between storage conditions in terms of total soluble solids and pH.

Refrigeration was found to slow the loss of vitamin C and the change in hardness.

Table 3: Chemical and physical properties of coated (C) and uncoated (NC) eggplant stored under refrigerated (7 ± 2 °C) and ambient (25 ± 2 °C) conditions.

Parameter	Sample	Storage time (days):					
		0	4	8	12	16	20
Moisture (%)	C7	91.8 ^{aA} ± 0.1	91.1 ^{aA} ± 0.0	89.7 ^{bA} ± 0.1	88.7 ^{cA} ± 0.04	86.9 ^{dA} ± 0.1	85.8 ^{dA} ± 0.1
	NC7	92.3 ^{aA} ± 0.2	90.8 ^{bAB} ± 0.0	89.4 ^{cA} ± 0.1	88.8 ^{cA} ± 0.03	86.8 ^{dA} ± 0.1	86.0 ^{dA} ± 0.0
	C26	91.8 ^{aA} ± 0.1	90.2 ^{bABC} ± 0.0	87.8 ^{cB} ± 0.2	85.4 ^{dB} ± 0.03	84.3 ^{dB} ± 0.3	80.2 ^{eB} ± 0.2
	NC26	92.3 ^{aA} ± 0.2	89.5 ^{bBC} ± 0.5	87.6 ^{cB} ± 0.2	85.3 ^{dB} ± 0.24	84.2 ^{dB} ± 0.2	80.5 ^{eB} ± 0.4
Weight loss (%)	C7	0.0 ^{cA} ± 0.0	1.1 ^{cB} ± 0.5	1.6 ^{cC} ± 0.2	4.6 ^{bC} ± 0.4	5.1 ^{bC} ± 0.9	8.5 ^{aB} ± 0.5
	NC7	0.0 ^{cA} ± 0.0	1.1 ^{cB} ± 0.4	2.4 ^{bC} ± 0.4	4.6 ^{abC} ± 0.4	5.4 ^{aC} ± 0.4	7.4 ^{aB} ± 0.2
	C26	0.0 ^{fA} ± 0.0	4.9 ^{eA} ± 0.8	8.7 ^{dB} ± 0.3	15.5 ^{cB} ± 3.6	20.0 ^{bB} ± 3.6	25.9 ^{aA} ± 0.1
	NC26	0.0 ^{eA} ± 0.0	5.6 ^{dA} ± 0.7	17.0 ^{cA} ± 0.3	22.3 ^{bA} ± 1.1	24.5 ^{abA} ± 1.6	26.9 ^{aA} ± 1.9

Total solid soluble (°Brix)	C7	4.1 ^{abA} ± 0.2	4.3 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.3 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.4 ^{aA} ± 0.1	4.50 ^{aA} ± 0.1	4.7 ^{aA} ± 0.1
	NC7	4.2 ^{abA} ± 0.0	4.3 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.3 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.4 ^{aA} ± 0.1	4.50 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.6 ^{aA} ± 0.1
	C26	4.2 ^{ba} ± 0.0	4.3 ^{ba} ± 0.1	4.4 ^{ba} ± 0.0	4.5 ^{abA} ± 0.1	4.70 ^{aA} ± 0.1	4.8 ^{aA} ± 0.1
	NC26	4.0 ^{cA} ± 0.1	4.2 ^{bcA} ± 0.0	4.4 ^{ba} ± 0.0	4.5 ^{abA} ± 0.1	4.80 ^{aA} ± 0.1	4.9 ^{aA} ± 0.1
pH	C7	4.9 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.8 ^{abA} ± 0.1	4.7 ^{abA} ± 0.0	4.75 ^{abA} ± 0.1	4.65 ^{bcA} ± 0.1	4.5 ^{cA} ± 0.1
	NC7	4.9 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.8 ^{abA} ± 0.1	4.7 ^{abA} ± 0.1	4.7 ^{abA} ± 0.0	4.60 ^{bcA} ± 0.0	4.6 ^{bcA} ± 0.0
	C26	4.9 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.7 ^{abAB} ± 0.1	4.6 ^{abA} ± 0.1	4.6 ^{abA} ± 0.1	4.60 ^{abA} ± 0.0	4.5 ^{ba} ± 0.0
	NC26	4.9 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.7 ^{abAB} ± 0.1	4.8 ^{abA} ± 0.0	4.6 ^{bcA} ± 0.0	4.50 ^{bcA} ± 0.0	4.5 ^{bcA} ± 0.1
Vitamin C (mg/100g)	C7	9.2 ^{aA} ± 0.1	8.6 ^{abA} ± 0.1	7.8 ^{bcA} ± 0.1	7.1 ^{cA} ± 0.2	6.07 ^{dA} ± 0.1	4.0 ^{eA} ± 0.0
	NC7	9.2 ^{aA} ± 0.3	8.5 ^{abA} ± 0.1	7.6 ^{bcA} ± 0.0	7.1 ^{cA} ± 0.0	6.14 ^{dA} ± 0.0	4.2 ^{eA} ± 0.1
	C26	9.2 ^{aA} ± 0.1	7.9 ^{ba} ± 0.0	6.2 ^{cB} ± 0.2	5.1 ^{dB} ± 0.1	3.05 ^{eB} ± 0.1	0.9 ^{fB} ± 0.1
	NC26	9.2 ^{aA} ± 0.3	7.8 ^{ba} ± 0.1	6.4 ^{cB} ± 0.1	5.0 ^{dB} ± 0.0	3.15 ^{eB} ± 0.1	1.1 ^{fB} ± 0.3
Hardness (N)	C7	0.2 ^{aA} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{aAB} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{abA} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{bcA} ± 0.0	0.18 ^{bcA} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{cA} ± 0.0
	NC7	0.2 ^{abA} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{abA} ± 0.0	0.3 ^{abA} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{abA} ± 0.0	0.19 ^{bcA} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{bcA} ± 0.0
	C26	0.2 ^{aA} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{bB} ± 0.0	0.1 ^{cB} ± 0.0	0.1 ^{dB} ± 0.0	0.09 ^{dB} ± 0.0	0.03 ^{eB} ± 0.0
	NC26	0.2 ^{aA} ± 0.0	0.2 ^{bB} ± 0.0	0.1 ^{bcB} ± 0.0	0.1 ^{cB} ± 0.0	0.084 ^{cB} ± 0.1	0.03 ^{dB} ± 0.0

Means within a row with the same lower-case superscript do not differ significantly. Means for the same parameter within a column with the same upper-case superscript do not differ significantly ($p < 0.05$).

The results of the microbiological analyses carried out on eggplant samples are reported in **Table 4**. The microbial counts (TPC and YMC) increased with storage in all samples, with a greater increase in the samples stored at ambient temperature than in those that were refrigerated. The coating did not cause a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in microbial growth between the refrigerated samples and those stored at room temperatures.

Table 4: Total plate count (TPC) and yeast and molds count (YMC) of coated (C) and uncoated (NC) eggplant stored under refrigerated ($7 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and ambient ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) conditions.

Parameter	Sample	Storage time (days)					
		0	4	8	12	16	20
TPC (log CFU/g)	C7	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{bb} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0
	NC7	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0
	C26	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0
	NC26	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	3.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0	4.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0
YMC (log CFU/g)	C7	0.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	0.0 ^{bb} ± 0.0	1.0 ^{ab} ± 0.0			
	NC7	0.0 ^{ca} ± 0.0	0.0 ^{cb} ± 0.0	1.0 ^{bb} ± 0.0	1.0 ^{bb} ± 0.0	1.0 ^{bb} ± 0.0	2.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0
	C26	0.0 ^{ca} ± 0.0	1.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	2.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0			
	NC26	0.0 ^{ca} ± 0.0	1.0 ^{ba} ± 0.0	2.0 ^{aA} ± 0.0			

Means within a row with the same lower-case superscript do not differ significantly. Means for the same parameter within a column with the same upper-case superscript do not differ significantly ($p < 0.05$).

The overall results showed that the use of the bio-based coating prototype on fresh eggplants did not significantly improve the product shelf-life. The possible reasons for the limited benefit of coating in maintaining the quality of the eggplants are not clear and require further investigation.

Validation

During the validation and training activities, the involved SMEs expressed a willingness to adopt the bio-based coating prototype for future operations (**Figure 15**). However, further activities are required to build the capacity of SMEs to produce and use the bio-based coatings in a sterile and standardized environment.

Figure 15: (a) Training and demonstration on production of bio-based packaging material with SMEs; (b) training and demonstration on production and application of bio-based packaging material with farmers/traders/processors in Masaka (UG).

2.2.1.3 UoN (KE)

Properties of packaging materials

The properties of the cassava starch/coconut oil-based with an average thickness of 150 μm and 200 μm were evaluated. The moisture content of the films increased with thickness and ranged from 9.9% for the 150 μm film to 10.2% for the 200 μm film. Thicker films (200 μm) showed lower transparency and higher water solubility compared to the thinner films (150 μm). After 4 months, biodegradation was 89.8% and 89.6% for the 200 μm and 150 μm film samples, respectively. The mechanical properties, including tensile strength, showed no significant differences between the two samples. These results demonstrate the potential of biofilm for sustainable packaging applications and at the same time highlight the thickness-dependent differences in performance attributes. The 200 μm film was selected for shelf-life studies. The specific results are reported in the Periodic Technical Report Part B and in the updated D4.11.

Shelf-life tests

Shelf-life studies were conducted on tree tomato fruit powder (*tamarillo*) and quinoa snacks (*mandazi*) (**Figure 16**), packaged with cassava starch/coconut oil-based film (200 μm) and with different type of commercially available flexible packaging materials (control). As control for Tamarillo powder was used Kraft paper laminated with LDPE, while for mandazi snacks were used: Kraft paper alone, Kraft paper laminated with LDPE, and metallized LDPE pouches.

The tamarillo powder was stored for 150 days, and the mandazi snacks for 5 days at 25 ± 2 °C. During the storage period the tamarillo powder was evaluated for water activity, moisture content, pH, colour, vitamins A and C, sensory properties and microbial growth, while the mandazi snack was evaluated for moisture content, free fatty acids (oleic acid) and microbial growth. All the analysis were done in triplicate.

Figure 16: (a) Tree tomato fruit powder (*tamarillo*) and sample packaged in the biodegradable film prototype; (b) ready to eat quinoa snack (*mandazi*) and sample differently packaged.

A total of 66 (33 + 33) pouches of tamarillo powder were produced, with samples being taken every 15 days until the microbial load (yeasts and molds) approached the specified limits after 150 days of storage. For the quinoa snacks, 24 pouches per type of packaging were produced.

Tree tomato fruit powder

The tamarillo powder was produced by drying the extracted pulp of the tree tomatoes in an innovative solar dryer. The results of the shelf-life test are shown in **Figure 17**, **Table 5**, **Figure 18** and **19**.

The water activity (a_w) for the packed tamarillo powder samples is shown in **Figure 17a**. The a_w value of the both packaged samples increased with increasing storage time. Initially, the average a_w value was 0.408 ± 0.00 , but after 150 days of storage, the value increased by 1.59% for the sample in biofilm and 1.47% for the control sample in laminated Kraft paper. Similarly, the moisture content of the samples increased with increasing storage time for both packaging conditions (**Figure 17b**). Initially, the average moisture content was 8.53 ± 0.36 , but after 150 days of storage, it increased in percentage terms by 1.47% for the sample in biofilm and 1.31% for the sample in laminated Kraft paper. As the storage period progressed, the pH of all samples generally decreased, regardless of the type of packaging, as can be seen in **Figure 17c**.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 17: (a) Changes in water activity, (b) moisture content, (c) pH of tree tomato fruit (tamarillo) powder packaged with cassava starch- and coconut oil-based packaging (biofilm) and conventional packaging material (Kraft paper laminated with LDPE) during storage. Asterisks indicate that there are significant differences among samples ($p < 0.05$).

The color parameters (CIEL*a*b*, C*, h°, ΔE*) and vitamins A and C results of the tamarillo powder samples packaged with the developed cassava-based film and conventional film (for comparison) at time 0 and after 150 days of storage are shown in **Table 5**. The color attributes were significantly ($p < 0.001$) affected by the storage period and packaging type. Moreover, both vitamins were significantly ($p < 0.001$) affected by the time of storage. Vitamin A content reduced by 78.35% and 77.51% in biofilm and laminated Kraft paper, respectively. Similarly, there was also a strong and similar reduction of vitamin C during the storage period by 86.08% and 86.88% in samples in biofilm and laminated Kraft paper, respectively.

The effect of the packaging and storage time on microbiological quality of tamarillo powder is shown in **Figure 18**. No growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* was detected in any of the samples during the entire storage time. The total viable count (TVC) was significantly different throughout the storage period ($p < 0.001$), with the highest average count found in the tamarillo powder packed in biofilm pouches after 150

days. No growth of yeasts and molds was detected in the first 15 days, but it started in both samples from 30 days of storage. The microbial load was significantly different ($p < 0.001$) with the highest count of 3.96 ± 0.06 Log CFU/g after 150 days in the sample packed with the biofilm material. However, the microbial load did not exceed the maximum values for dried fruit powder, which are 6 (log CFU/g) for TVC and 4 (log CFU/g) for yeasts and molds (Mendonca et al., 2020). This shows that the tamarillo powder in both packages met the microbiological safety standards after 150 days of storage, even though the microbial load in the sample packed in the control material was always lower.

Table 5: Changes in color, vitamins A and C of tree tomato fruit (tamarillo) powder packaged with cassava starch/coconut oil-based packaging (biofilm) and conventional packaging material (Kraft paper laminated with LDPE) at day 0 and after 150 days of storage.

Packaging material	Day	L*	C*	h°	ΔE^*	Vitamin A (mg/100 g)	Vitamin C (mg/100 g)
Before packaging	0	25.85±0.45 ^a	11.33±0.42 ^a	31.03±1.25 ^a	-	49.23±0.59 ^a	351.01±3.4 ^a
Biofilm	150	21.54±0.57 ^a	7.50±0.50 ^c	19.99±0.18 ^b	23.11±0.60 ^a	10.66±0.89 ^b	46.32±5.57 ^b
Kraft paper laminated with LDPE	150	21.99±0.27 ^{bc}	8.17±0.11 ^{bc}	22.47±1.23 ^b	22.59±0.34 ^a	11.07±0.77 ^b	46.07±3.46 ^b

Values with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

a)

b)

Figure 18: (a) Total viable count - TVC (log CFU/g) and (b) total yeast and molds count (log CFU/g) of tree tomato fruit (tamarillo) powder packaged with cassava starch/coconut oil-based packaging (biofilm) and conventional packaging material (Kraft paper laminated with LDPE) during storage. Asterisks indicate that there are significant differences among samples ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 19: Effect of packaging materials and storage on sensory attributes of tree tomato fruit (tamarillo) powder packaged with cassava starch/coconut oil-based packaging (biofilm) and conventional packaging materials (Kraft paper laminated with LDPE) during storage. Different letters indicate significant differences among the samples ($p < 0.05$).

The average sensory test results are shown in **Figure 19**. The results of the sensory analysis showed significant differences ($p < 0.001$) in terms of tamarillo powder' appearance, taste, texture, aroma and general acceptability between day 0 and after 150 days of storage. This clearly shows that the storage period and packaging influenced the quality characteristics of tamarillo powder. After 150 days of storage, on the average the tamarillo powder packaged in conventional material was more acceptable for all tested

quality attributes than the sample packed in the biofilm; however, no significant differences were found between the two differently packed samples.

According to the results, it seems that the bio-based material is suitable to preserve the tamarillo powder quality for 150 days at ambient conditions similarly to the LDPE laminated Kraft paper material.

Quinoa snack (mandazi)

The mandazi snacks were prepared by first mixing the dry ingredients (quinoa flour, wheat flour, sugar, salt, baking powder and yeast). Then ghee (clarified butter) was added and mixed with the dry ingredients until the dough mixture appeared buttered and granule-like. Warm water (30-40 °C) was added sequentially with kneading the dough by hands. After kneading, the dough was matured by covering with a wet cloth for about 45 minutes. The dough was then reworked for about 1 min and then, divided into 240 g dough balls. The dough batches (balls) were then flatten like a pizza bread, divided into 4 equal part and shaped. The cut dough in mandazi shape was then deep-fried using palm oil under medium heat for 2 minutes, then put in a metallic bucket for cooling.

The results of the mandazi snack shelf-life test are shown in **Figure 20**. The moisture content (**Figure 20a**) of the samples was significantly different ($p < 0.005$) and increased with storage time for each of the packaging materials. It was highest for the biofilm sample with an increase of 29.76% and lowest for the laminated Kraft paper with an increase of 14.59%. The sample in LDPE laminated with kraft paper underwent the lowest moisture increase during storage.

a)

b)

Figure 20: Changes in moisture content (a) and free fatty acids - FFA content (b) of quinoa snack (mandazi) packaged with cassava starch/coconut oil-based packaging (biofilm) and conventional packaging materials (Kraft paper laminated with LDPE, Kraft paper, metallized LDPE pouches) during storage. Asterisks indicate that there are significant differences among samples ($p < 0.05$).

The free fatty acids (FFA) (**Figure 20b**) of the samples increased with increase in storage period for each of the packaging materials with the highest recorded in the biofilm and lowest in the LDPE laminated Kraft paper. The FFA content is considered to be a quality indicator in the product as it leads to development of off-flavor in the fried products due to the accelerated hydrolysis of the triglycerides.

However, from the microbiological results there was no growth of indicator organisms (coliforms), yeasts and molds and therefore the product was microbiologically safe. This could be attributed to the good hygiene practices and deep frying of the quinoa snacks which destroyed any microbe present.

The bio-based film produced was not effective in maintaining the shelf-life of the mandazi snack compared to the conventional film studied, indicating the need for further improvements for this application.

Validation

Feedback from 38 participants who attended the field innovation validation at Kitui Food Hub (KEPC) was collected using questionnaires on acceptance of the bio-based packaging prototype (**Figure 21**).

Figure 21: (a) Forming and sealing of the bio-based film pouches and packaging of tree tomato fruit powder for industrial testing at Kitui Food Hub; (b) processors and farmers appreciating the packaging prototype at Kitui Food Hub.

The percentage of participants who think that the acceptance parameters listed in **Table 6** are extremely likely varies between 68.4 % and 89.5 %, while the percentage of those who think that the acceptance parameters are quite likely ranges between 7.9 and 23.7%. The majority of participants (89.4%) indicated that they intend to use cassava starch/coconut oil-based film packaging as soon as it becomes available, highlighting positive feedback from the validation survey.

Table 6: Bio-based packaging made of cassava starch/coconut oil acceptance (percent of respondents).

ACCEPTANCE PARAMETERS	LIKELY				UNLIKELY		
	Extremely	Quite	Slightly	Neither	Slightly	Quite	Extremely
Using this pack. technology would be	86.8	13.2	0	0	0	0	0

useful in packaging solid foods							
Using this pack. technology would reduce food losses	73.7	15.8	2.6	5.3	2.6	0	0
Using this technology would solve the problem of plastics pollution	89.5	7.9	2.6	0	0	0	0
Learning to operate the bio-based packaging system would be easy for me	68.4	23.7	2.6	5.3	0	0	0
I would find the bio-based packaging technology easy to use	84.2	10.5	2.6	2.6	0	0	0
I have the intention to use this technology when it becomes available	78.9	10.5	0	2.6	0	0	8.0

N=38.

2.2.1.4 SUA (TZ)

Proprieties of packaging materials

The most important properties of the developed films based on PPs nanocellulose were evaluated. The overall results, both in terms of mechanical and chemical properties, show that pineapple peels (PPs) are a potential material source for the production of bio-based films that can be used for food packaging, but in combination with secondary packaging. Depending on the PPnc concentration used in the film formulation, the packaging films exhibited different properties, with thickness ranging between 60 and 80 μm and moisture content respectively between 10.9-14.1%. The transparency values were similar for all formulations and ranged from 23.9% to 24.5%. The biodegradation rate was high, ranging from 86.4% to 91.1% after 4 weeks, in addition to relatively stable values for water and acid solubility. Furthermore, the tensile strength was between 68.6 MPa and 72.4 MPa, indicating good mechanical properties of the films. The film formulated with 12% of PPnc (of gellan gum, w/w) was selected for shelf-life studies. The specific results are reported in the Periodic Technical Report Part B and in the updated D4.11.

Shelf-life tests

A shelf-life study of extruded and non-extruded composite flours (comprising 60% white maize, 15% biofortified common beans, 10% millet, 10% soybeans, and 5% sesame) was conducted (**Figure 22a**). Extruded flour is a ready-to-use flour for porridge

preparation, while the non-extruded one requires cooking. Briefly, the composite flour samples of about 250 g were packed in three types of packaging materials: (i) 12% PPnc-based pouch inserted in a paper pouch (secondary packaging) (**Figure 22b** and **22c**), (ii) paper pouch and (iii) polyethylene pouch (**Figure 22d**). The samples were stored at two different temperatures: room (25 ± 3 °C) and refrigerated temperature (4 ± 1 °C) for 5 months. Relative humidity was monitored throughout the experiment; on average, at room temperature conditions the relative humidity was of $65 \pm 5\%$ (with a minimum of 60% and a maximum of 70%), while at the refrigerated environment was around $85 \pm 5\%$.

Figure 22: (a) Extruded (left) and non-extruded flour (right) at the beginning of shelf-life study (time 0); (b) composite flour sample packaged in PPs nanocellulose (PPnc)-based film alone; (c) composite flour sample packaged in PPs nanocellulose-based (primary packaging) and paper pouches (secondary packaging); (d) composite flour sample packed in polyethylene pouches (control).

For each flour product, packaging condition and storage conditions 240 pouches were prepared (10 x 3 packaging types = 30 pouches x 2 storage conditions = 60 pouches x 2 flour type = 120 pouches x two repetitions = 240 pouches in total). The samples were collected in duplicate every sampling time (eleven time points: 0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, 105, 120, 135 and 150 days) and evaluated for physicochemical properties and microbial

quality: moisture content, water activity, colour (CIEL*a*b*), total bacteria, yeasts and molds (**Figure 23**).

Figure 23: Experimental design of the shelf-life studies (SUA, TZ).

Extruded composite flour

Tables 7 and **8** report the quality characteristics of the extruded composite flour packaged in different materials after 0, 90 and 150 days of storage at room temperature ($25 \pm 3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and at refrigeration temperature ($4 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), respectively.

Table 7: Initial and final characteristics of extruded flour at room temperature ($25 \pm 3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) conditions packed in bio-based (+ paper), paper and polyethylene pouches.

Parameters	0 day	Bio-based (+ paper)		Paper		Polyethylene	
		90 days	150 days	90 days	150 days	90 days	150 days
Moisture (%)	4.52 ± 0.05	11.25 ± 0.01	11.77 ± 0.01	12.38 ± 0.01	13.05 ± 0.60	12.15 ± 0.01	12.57 ± 0.62
Water activity (a_w)	0.63 ± 0.00	0.62 ± 0.00	0.80 ± 0.00	0.62 ± 0.00	0.80 ± 0.04	0.62 ± 0.00	0.73 ± 0.00
L*	89.27 ± 0.00	85.13 ± 0.06	86.75 ± 1.24	85.11 ± 0.06	98.22 ± 0.69	85.45 ± 0.06	83.98 ± 0.86
b*	20.04 ± 0.21	20.18 ± 0.00	22.91 ± 0.37	16.19 ± 0.03	21.23 ± 2.36	19.86 ± 0.00	22.87 ± 0.45

Yeast (log CFU/g)	2.14 ± 0.04	2.46 ± 0.00	3.82 ± 0.07	2.46 ± 0.01	3.78 ± 0.07	2.30 ± 0.00	3.59 ± 0.01
Molds (log CFU/g)	0.00 ± 0.00	1.98 ± 0.50	3.40 ± 0.08	2.04 ± 0.50	3.59 ± 0.18	2.01 ± 0.00	3.80 ± 0.68
Total bacteria (log CFU/g)	0.00 ± 0.00	3.02 ± 0.40	3.91 ± 0.10	2.50 ± 0.00	3.97 ± 0.00	2.56 ± 0.00	3.95 ± 0.00

Table 8: Initial and final characteristics of extruded flour at refrigerated temperature (4 ± 1 °C) conditions packed in bio-based (+ paper), paper and polyethylene pouches.

Parameters	Bio-based (+ paper)			Paper		Polyethylene	
	0 day	90 days	150 days	90 days	150 days	90 days	150 days
Moisture (%)	4.52 ± 0.05	12.90 ± 0.01	13.07 ± 0.21	10.70 ± 0.01	12.92 ± 0.28	12.47 ± 0.00	13.76 ± 0.05
Water activity (a_w)	0.63 ± 0.00	0.60 ± 0.00	0.79 ± 0.00	0.63 ± 0.00	0.72 ± 0.00	0.64 ± 0.00	0.72 ± 0.00
L*	89.27 ± 0.00	85.64 ± 0.06	88.47 ± 1.04	89.38 ± 0.06	86.21 ± 0.52	90.79 ± 0.00	83.63 ± 1.99
b*	20.04 ± 0.21	20.23 ± 0.04	20.59 ± 1.49	15.10 ± 0.05	21.66 ± 0.7	15.87 ± 0.16	18.55 ± 0.53
Yeast (log CFU/g)	2.14 ± 0.04	2.34 ± 0.00	3.84 ± 0.08	2.09 ± 0.00	3.96 ± 0.01	2.26 ± 0.00	3.78 ± 0.07
Molds (log CFU/g)	0.00 ± 0.00	1.56 ± 0.50	3.85 ± 0.03	1.96 ± 0.00	3.90 ± 0.07	1.61 ± 0.00	3.18 ± 0.02
Total bacteria (log CFU/g)	0.00 ± 0.00	3.20 ± 0.00	3.90 ± 0.07	2.56 ± 0.01	3.97 ± 0.00	3.05 ± 0.00	3.72 ± 0.03

The moisture content of the extruded flour increases during the storage period regardless of the type of packaging, but no substantial differences were found between the packaging types under both ambient and refrigerated conditions.

The water activity (a_w) of the extruded flour also increased over time under both storage conditions. At room temperature, the polythene packaging maintained the most stable levels, while the bio-based (+paper) and paper pouches showed greater a_w values. No considerable differences were found between the samples when stored at refrigeration temperature.

As far as the colour of the extruded flour is concerned, L* (lightness) shows a material-dependent variation. At room temperature, L* of the flour decreases in the flour with bio-based and polyethylene packaging, while it increases in paper-packaged samples. At refrigerated temperature (4°C), all samples showed a decrease in L*. At room temperature, the parameter b* (yellow intensity) increases in all samples regardless of the packaging, whereas this was less clear under refrigerated conditions.

Microbial growth also varied depending on the storage conditions. At room temperature, the yeast, mold and total bacterial counts increased in all extruded flour samples regardless of the type of packaging. The sample with the paper pouch packaging had the highest total bacterial growth, while the sample in bio-based and polyethylene had the lowest. In general, the flour packaged in bio-based (+paper) pouch had microbial counts between those of the other two samples. Under refrigeration, the flour packaged in bio-based (+paper) and paper pouches still had slightly higher microbial counts compared to polyethylene.

Non-extruded composite flour

Tables 9 and 10 report the quality characteristics of the non-extruded composite flour packaged in the various materials after 0, 90 and 150 days of storage at room temperature (25 ± 3 °C) and at refrigeration temperature (4 ± 1 °C), respectively.

Table 9: Initial and final characteristics of non-extruded flour at room temperature (25 ± 3 °C) conditions packed in bio-based (+ paper), paper and polyethylene pouches.

Parameters	Bio-based (+ paper)			Paper		Polyethylene	
	0 day	90 days	150 days	90 days	150 days	90 days	150 days
Moisture (%)	6.32 ± 0.01	12.39 ± 0.01	12.97 ± 0.0	11.25 ± 0.01	12.75 ± 0.00	12.38 ± 0.01	12.62 ± 0.06
Water activity (a_w)	0.64 ± 0.00	0.62 ± 0.00	0.79 ± 0.00	0.62 ± 0.00	0.79 ± 0.04	0.62 ± 0.00	0.73 ± 0.00
L*	89.86 ± 0.00	85.13 ± 0.06	93.56 ± 1.24	85.11 ± 0.00	97.82 ± 2.80	89.37 ± 0.04	90.38 ± 2.64
b*	15.57 ± 0.63	19.86 ± 0.00	20.89 ± 0.07	16.50 ± 0.00	21.16 ± 1.56	15.48 ± 0.00	19.11 ± 0.15
Yeast (log CFU/g)	2.59 ± 0.12	2.09 ± 0.01	3.81 ± 0.03	2.67 ± 0.01	3.96 ± 0.01	2.47 ± 0.00	3.61 ± 0.20
Molds (log CFU/g)	0.00 ± 0.00	1.98 ± 0.00	3.49 ± 0.08	1.54 ± 0.00	3.90 ± 0.01	2.00 ± 0.01	3.60 ± 0.01
Total bacteria (log CFU/g)	0.00 ± 0.00	2.22 ± 0.00	3.87 ± 0.08	2.13 ± 0.00	3.87 ± 0.07	2.26 ± 0.00	3.94 ± 0.67

Table 10: Initial and final characteristics of non-extruded flour at refrigerated temperature (4 ± 1 °C) conditions packed in bio-based (+ paper), paper and polyethylene pouches.

Parameters	Bio-based (+ paper)			Paper		Polyethylene	
	0 day	90 days	150 days	90 days	150 days	90 days	150 days
Moisture (%)	6.32 ± 0.01	13.83 ± 0.02	13.29 ± 0.60	10.12 ± 0.01	13.42 ± 0.40	10.70 ± 0.01	13.95 ± 0.02
Water activity (a_w)	0.64 ± 0.00	0.62 ± 0.00	0.72 ± 0.00	0.64 ± 0.00	0.75 ± 0.00	0.63 ± 0.00	0.72 ± 0.00
L*	89.86 ± 0.00	85.64 ± 0.06	91.27 ± 1.65	89.38 ± 0.00	89.34 ± 3.09	90.50 ± 0.04	87.84 ± 3.10
b*	15.57 ± 0.63	20.23 ± 0.04	20.03 ± 0.47	20.87 ± 0.01	21.84 ± 0.64	21.04 ± 0.04	22.98 ± 0.64
Yeast (log CFU/g)	2.59 ± 0.12	2.09 ± 0.00	3.94 ± 0.06	2.12 ± 0.00	3.84 ± 0.00	2.37 ± 0.00	3.90 ± 0.00
Molds (log CFU/g)	0.00 ± 0.00	3.48 ± 0.07	3.80 ± 0.06	2.08 ± 0.00	3.71 ± 0.01	2.16 ± 0.00	3.81 ± 0.02
Total bacteria (log CFU/g)	0.00 ± 0.00	2.84 ± 0.00	3.60 ± 0.07	2.56 ± 0.01	3.77 ± 0.04	3.94 ± 0.07	3.09 ± 0.21

At room and refrigerated temperatures, all non-extruded flour samples showed an increase in moisture, but without substantial differences between the packaging types. Water activity followed a similar trend, increasing slightly over time in all samples, with the non-extruded flour packed in polyethylene pouch showing the most stability of this parameter.

The results obtained for colour show that there was only a slight variation between samples. At room temperature, the flour packaged in bio-based (+paper) pouch maintained a better L^* level compared to the paper pouch but showed a greater increase than polyethylene. The b^* parameter increased in all flour samples, with the paper and bio-based packaging showing the most significant changes, while polyethylene offered better colour stability. Similar trends were also observed under refrigerated conditions, however the differences between samples were less evident.

At room temperature, yeast, molds and bacterial growth increased in all samples, but after 150 days of storage, the flour packaged in paper pouches had the highest yeast and molds counts, while the flour packaged in polyethylene and bio-based pouches had the lowest. Microbial growth was slightly slower under refrigeration, but not in all samples. The non-extruded flour packaged in a bio-based (+paper) pouch was even more similar to that packaged in the paper pouch than the polyethylene pouch.

Overall, the bio-based (+paper) pouch performed slightly well in maintaining the quality characteristics of both types of composite flours, but not as effectively as the polyethylene packaging material. Further improvements are needed to increase the performance of the bio-based film, especially for long-term storage (> 90 days) of dried food products.

2.2.1.4 LCA and LCC of the new packaging solutions

Compared to conventional low-density polyethylene (LDPE) packaging material, which was used as the standard reference, the bio-based packaging prototypes developed had a consistently lower environmental impact according to the life cycle assessment (LCA) results. This indicates that bio-based packaging materials are a more sustainable alternative to conventional LDPE and reduce environmental impacts such as greenhouse gas emissions. In particular, the percentages reduction in kg CO₂ equivalent per kilogram (kg CO₂-eq/kg) emissions between the LDPE packaging material and the wheat straw nanocellulose-based film (INAT), the cassava starch/chitosan-based film and coating (NARO, MAK), the cassava starch/coconut oil-based film (UoN) and the pineapple peels nanocellulose-based film (SUA) are 40.9%, 71.2% and 74.9%, 83.8% and 75.2%, respectively.

In terms of life cycle costing (LCC) results, the production costs of the new bio-based films were generally higher than those of the conventional LDPE film, with the exception of INAT's wheat straw nanocellulose-based film. Specifically, the costs for 500 cm² of cassava starch/chitosan-based film (NARO, MAK), cassava starch/coconut oil-based film (UoN) and pineapple peel nanocellulose-based film (SUA) are 873%, 14% and 923% higher than LDPE, respectively. In contrast, the cost of wheat straw nanocellulose-based film (INAT) is approximately 73% lower than LDPE film.

Specific results on LCA and LCC analysis are reported in the Zenodo database at the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14918187>.

2.2.2 Relevant production

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- “Training Session on Bio-Based Packaging for Agricultural Products” at INAT (TN), April 26, 2024, led by Ines Ben Rejeb and organized by Faten Khamassi.
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NARO (UG)

None.

MAK (UG)

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UoN (KE)

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SUA (TZ)

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UNIBO (IT)

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2.3 Summary of the outcomes

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Jendouba (TN) - INAT	<p>New biobased packaging material for mild-dried vegetable/fruit products (eggplants and strawberries) made of: PBAT (polybutylene adipate terephthalate), TPS (plasticized starch, CNC (cellulose nanocrystalline) and natural antioxidant.</p> <p>- CNC obtained from wheat straw fibers and antioxidant extract from artichoke by-products were used in the material formulation to enhance mechanical properties, barrier performance and antioxidant functionality.</p> <p>- The sustainability of bio-based packaging through its renewable composition and low kg CO₂-eq/kg emissions compared to conventional LDPE material was demonstrated.</p>	1 - GDA Beni Mtir

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preliminary shelf-life tests on soft-dried eggplants/strawberries packaged with the bio-based film compared to conventional material were carried out. 	
Kajjansi / Masaka (UG) - NARO	<p>New biobased packaging film and coating for fish products (soft-smoked fish fillets and deep-fried fish fingers) made of: cassava starch and chitosan.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bio-based film and coating with good physical-chemical properties and optimised viscosity were obtained. - The sustainability of bio-based packaging through its renewable composition, biodegradability and low kg CO₂-eq/kg emissions compared to conventional LDPE material was assessed. - A good preservation of the quality characteristics of soft-smoked fish fillets when coated with the bio-based coating was assessed. - Demonstration of the new bio-based coating preparation and application on fish products to local SMEs, farmers/traders/processors were done. 	30 farmers 3 SMEs
Nakaseke (UG) - MAK		1 SME
Kitui (KE) - UoN	<p>New biobased packaging material for tree tomato powder (tamarillo) and quinoa-based snack (mandazi) made of: cassava starch and coconut oil.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bio-based film with good physical-chemical properties was obtained. - The sustainability of bio-based packaging through its renewable composition, biodegradability and low kg CO₂-eq/kg emissions compared to conventional LDPE material was assessed. - A good preservation of the quality characteristics of tamarillo powder packaged with bio-based film compared to conventional material was demonstrated. - Demonstration of the new bio-based film pouches preparation for tamarillo powder to local SME and farmers with positive feedback was done. 	38 farmers * 1 SME
Mvomero, Morogoro (TZ) - SUA	<p>New biobased packaging material for extruded and non-extruded composite flour made of: nanocellulose from pineapple peels and gellan gum.</p>	20 farmers 1 SME

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bio-based film with good physical-chemical properties was obtained. - The sustainability of bio-based packaging through its renewable composition, biodegradability and low kg CO₂-eq/kg emissions compared to conventional LDPE material was assessed. - Demonstration of the new bio-based film preparation and application on composite flours to a local SME was done. 	
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* Although the Kitui Food (KE) Hub has 800 farmers, only 38 farmers from each Food Hub were directly involved in the validation activities. Validation work was not done at Mukurweini Food Hub as Tamarillo Kenya Ltd. withdrew from the FoodLAND Project.

2.4 Summary of the impacts

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Jendouba (TN) - INAT	Bio-based packaging material, made of: PBAT (polybutylene adipate terephthalate), TPS (plasticized starch), CNC (cellulose nanocrystalline) and antioxidant extract.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improvement or similarity of total phenolic content (TPC) of mild-dried food products packaged in bio-based packaging compared to conventional packaging (Eggplants packaged in the new bio-based packaging had a 45.2% higher TPC content than those packaged in polypropylene (PP) after four months of storage at 35 °C. Strawberries packaged in the new bio-based packaging had comparable TPC values to those packaged in PP after four months of storage at 35 °C). - Reduction of kg CO₂-eq/kg emissions by 40.9% compared to conventional LDPE packaging material.
Kajjansi / Masaka (UG) - NARO Nakaseke (UG) - MAK	Bio-based packaging materials (film and coating) made of: cassava starch and chitosan.	- Improvement of the microbiological quality of soft-smoked fish fillets coated with a bio-based packaging + LDPE film compared to the uncoated + LDPE film one (75.6% less total plate

		<p>count and 41.2% less yeast and molds count in the coated sample).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of kg CO₂-eq/kg emissions by 71.2% and 74.9% compared to conventional LDPE packaging material for film and coating.
Kitui (KE) - UoN	Bio-based packaging material, made of: cassava starch and coconut oil.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comparable quality in terms of VitA and VitC values between the samples of tree tomato powder packaged in the new and the conventional (LDPE-laminated Kraft paper) material after 150 days of storage at 25 °C. - Reduction of kg CO₂-eq/kg emissions by 83.8% compared to conventional LDPE packaging material.
Mvomero, Morogoro (TZ) - SUA	Bio-based packaging material, made of: pineapple peels nanocellulose and gellan gum.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Similarity of microbiological quality of composite flours packaged in bio-based + paper packaging compared to conventional packaging (non-extruded flour had similar total bacterial and molds counts to polyethylene (PE) packaged flour after 150 days of storage at 25 °C and similar yeast and molds counts after 150 days of storage at 4 °C. After 150 days of storage at 25 °C, extruded flour had a similar total bacterial count as flour packaged in PE). - Reduction of kg CO₂-eq/kg emissions by 75.2% compared to conventional LDPE packaging material.

3. Protocol for the implementation

3.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

The developed prototypes of bio-based packaging materials were primarily intended for use in the food sector, i.e. for packaging manufacturers and food producers. The most important properties of the innovative bio-based materials include biodegradability, environmental sustainability (LCA) and food suitability. The sustainability of the developed packaging materials is also related to the main use of by-products as ingredients (e.g. wheat straw fibres, artichoke by-products, bitter cassava roots, pineapple peels) from local agricultural/food companies/farmers.

Despite their advantages, bio-based materials prototypes may have some limitations, in some cases are mainly due to the lack of specific technological properties, in other cases due to the high production costs or the difficulty of scaling-up.

Therefore, further experiments need to be carried out to improve certain properties of some of the developed materials, in particular oxygen and water vapour barrier, machinability and sealing performances. Moreover, according to the LCC analysis, the production costs for almost all prototypes are higher than for conventional plastic (LDPE), and scaling up production over large batches can pose a challenge for the cost efficiency of the new materials.

In addition, the production of these prototypes still involves many manual steps that must be carried out under aseptic/sterile conditions to prevent their contamination that could compromise the food safety. Another challenge that needs to be taken into account is the procurement of the required raw materials (various by-products) in large quantities, during almost of the entire year and with as constant as possible quality characteristics. Furthermore, the higher sensibility of bio-based materials to storage conditions (e.g. temperature, relative humidity, light, etc.) compared to petroleum-based plastics must be taken into account in order to better manage their use and maintain their performance for food applications.

Both compliance and the lack of strict local regulations on food packaging, plastic materials and waste management remain critical issues that need to be considered and assessed. In Tunisia, for example, the regulatory framework for packaging materials, including bio-based materials, includes laws such as Law No. 87-2007 (packaging and waste management), Law No. 93-34 (food safety regulations), Decree No. 95-1193 (materials in contact with food), the national INNORPI standards and the Codex Alimentarius. In Uganda, the National Environment Act No. 5 of 2019 bans plastic carrier bags smaller than 30 microns, although implementation is still ongoing, which could hinder the growth of bio-based packaging adoption. In Kenya, the government has strictly limited the use of low-thickness plastic films and is encouraging the development and use of bio-based packaging materials, but without much specific information on certification and controls. Tanzania also has regulations such as the requirements of the standards for packaging and environment - organic recycling standards requirements, pre-packaging and labelling of foods (TZS 538: 2015(E)), packaging - flexible carrier

bags (TZS 2292:2018/EAS 882:2018(E)), solid waste management - non- hazardous waste (TZS 2265:2018(E)), which are promoted by public authorities such as the Tanzania Bureau of Standards (TBS).

To summarise, while the new prototypes of bio-based packaging materials developed offer significant benefits in terms of environmental sustainability and food quality preservation, they may also face some challenges related to high production costs, availability of raw materials on a large scale and potential compliance with local specific regulations that need to be assessed.

3.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

INAT (TN)

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Raw materials:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - wheat straw fibers - artichoke by-products - sodium hydroxide sodium - aqueous sodium chlorite - glacial acetic acid - sulfuric acid solution - glycerol - PBAT - starch 	M
2	<i>Equipment:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - semi-industrial scale electric crusher - heating hotplate - laboratory centrifuge - twin screw extrusion machine - blown film machine 	M
3	<i>Energy consumption (electricity) for:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - drying raw material/cellulose - crushing - heating - mechanical stirring - centrifugation + sonication - extruder - forming the pouches with the sealing machine 	M
4	<i>Water usage</i>	M
5	<i>Possibly transport:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - transport raw straw fibers/artichoke by-products collection - travel for using the extruder 	2

	* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low
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NARO and MAK (UG)

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Raw materials: fresh cassava roots (bitter varieties e.g. Magana), chitosan, glycerol, acetic acid</i>	M
2	<i>Potable water/Distilled water</i>	M/1
3	<i>Equipment: mechanised grater, drying oven, heater with stirring, laboratory mill</i>	M
4	<i>Energy: electricity and fuel</i>	M
5	<i>**Moulding trays preferably plastic or stainless steel</i>	M
	* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low	

***Requirements for bio-based film - additional.*

UoN (KE)

Ref.	Requirement description**	Priority*
1	<i>Cassava starch processing machine incorporating cage type cassava cleaning and peeling machine, crushing separator, fine filter and starch dehydrator</i>	M
2	<i>Mixing vessel, complete with electric heater and stirrer</i>	M
3	<i>Biodegradable film blowing machine (extruder)</i>	M
4	<i>Raw materials:</i> - <i>cassava tubers</i> - <i>coconut oil</i> - <i>glycerol</i>	M
5	<i>Distilled water</i>	M
	* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low	

*** Requirement description for large production scale.*

SUA (TZ)

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Raw materials:</i> - <i>pineapple peels</i> - <i>sodium hypochlorite</i> - <i>sodium hydroxide</i> - <i>sulphuric acid</i> - <i>gellan gum</i> - <i>glycerol</i>	M

	- ethanol	
2	Water or distilled water	M/1
9	Filter paper Whatman n. 1	M
10	Knife or peeler of pineapples	M
11	Drier (oven)	M
12	Centrifuge	M
13	Freeze drier	M
14	Sonicator for mixing	M
15	Molding for film casting	M
16	Cutting machine	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

3.3 Management for the bio-based materials production in an industrial environment

The management of the bio-based packaging materials production in an industrial environment requires a comprehensive and structured approach. This could include, for example, the introduction of standard operating procedures (SOPs), customised protocols and optimised workflows specifically tailored to SMEs wishing to use these innovative materials. In addition, regular technical inspections and audits by qualified teams are essential to ensure compliance with a robust quality management system. These measures are crucial to ensure consistently high and constant quality characteristics (both technological and food grade) of the final bio-based packaging materials.

To maintain high standards of product materials, quality control systems should be integrated into every stage of production, from sourcing local raw materials to testing the final product. This ensures the monitoring of critical properties of the bio-based materials such as mechanical strength, biodegradability and barrier performance. In addition, continuous assessments, including environmental impact ones and analyses of customer feedback, are necessary to refine packaging prototypes, improve performances and ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and industry standards.

Collaboration between key stakeholders, including raw material suppliers, production managers, workers, quality control personnel and regulatory authorities, is fundamental to the successful implementation and scaling of bio-based materials.

Through these strategic management and control measures, bio-based packaging materials could be easily produced on an industrial scale and their quality, safety and competitiveness guaranteed in the long term.

4. Conclusions

The development and implementation of prototypes of bio-based materials is an important step on the way to sustainable food packaging solutions that offer an alternative to conventional plastics and contribute to environmental protection. The African partners involved have shown that it is possible to produce bio-based materials from local agricultural product and by-products that have demonstrable environmental benefits and are in line with the principles of the circular economy.

However, further studies are still needed to improve the barrier, mechanical and sealing properties of the new bio-based material prototypes and to bring their performance and applications for food packaging as close as possible to those of conventional plastics.

Scaling their production remains another challenge, as maintaining consistent and constant quality and cost efficiency on an industrial scale is crucial for widespread adoption by SMEs. In addition, the need for more comprehensive and broad local regulations for food packaging, plastic materials and waste management is essential for their market development.

Moreover, the development of recycling and composting infrastructures is crucial to ensure that these materials can be effectively integrated into existing waste management systems. The promotion of eco-labelling and certification for biodegradable materials may also be necessary to raise consumer awareness, facilitate proper disposal and support the transition to a more sustainable packaging ecosystem.

Strengthening collaboration between research institutions, industry representatives and policy makers will be crucial to support the improvement of prototypes and the implementation/transfer to industrial scale, thus contributing to a more sustainable food packaging system.

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